

This is a reference and summary document to the paper published in Electric Power Systems, referred to the CleanSky2 H2020 project [E-TSIN](#): Modular, scalable, multi-functional, high power density power controller for electrical taxi: In this paper, a field oriented control based strategy is proposed in order to control two voltage source inverter connected in parallel feeding an only load, in this case, a PMSM.

This proposal presented by Indra Sistemas and CEIT jointly, try to answer in the best way the call JTI-CS2-2014-CFP01-SYS-02-02.

The referred call and this associated proposal are framed inside of the packet 4.1.2.4 (Modular power controller for advanced landing system) of the System ITD for the CleanSky2 project. This project will develop a next generation power controller for electrical taxi. This controller shall feature increased power density, bidirectional power conversion, modularity, scalability, and multifunctionality to support wide range of aircraft applications. Inside this global project of aircraft electrical moving on ground (e-TAXI), this concrete WP, try to answer the necessity of electrical power converters to:

- Supply new electrical motors inside of the landing gear system (getting energy from electrical sources inside the aircraft)
- Re-charge dedicated batteries inside the aircraft for the landing gear system. This function will help to have additional power available in batteries to be used when necessary, as in acceleration moments. Moreover, the re-charge will be done when aircraft speed on ground is enough or there is a necessity of braking (producing electrical braking over the motors).

Then, proposal solution in this call develops a solution answering both functions and getting a global optimization of the system. This solution is done in accordance with aeronautical standards (environmental constraints), where the participants in this proposal have a vast experience.

This proposal is presented by the consortium INDRA & CEIT that have all competences and skills to develop this project in time and performances, based in its experience in bidirectional and modular power electronic converters and well-known aeronautic standards, rules and process, more when Indra base its business in manufacturing of aeronautic equipment and system, totally verified and qualified.

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- This paper reflects only the author's view and that the JU is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

FOC-Droop control strategy for PMSM fed paralleled multi-inverter power systems oriented to aeronautical applications

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Abstract—This paper proposes a Field Oriented Control (FOC) for a Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine (PMSM) which is supplied by a Parallel Multi-Inverter System. The parallelization of the Voltage Source Inverters is safely achieved using a V-F Droop Control strategy as a distributed generation system would be considered like in Smart-Grids. This novel technique is the combination of the previous mentioned both strategies, and will be key when answering to the need of modularity, scalability, redundancy and parallelization for electrical machine control systems. Theoretical and experimental analysis are provided in order to validate the new combined control strategy which fulfills the motor control requirements while current balancing is safely achieved between individual parallelized inverters

Index Terms—FOC, PMSM, Multi-Inverter System, Droop, Parallelization

A. Highlights

A Parallel Multi-Inverter System feeding a PMSM is proposed as a solution for MEA Electric Taxiing.

Novel control technique based on a combination of FOC and Droop control achieves motor control and equal current sharing among inverters.

Experimental results validate control strategy fulfilling motor control and application requirements.

- I. INTRODUCTION
- II. BASIC STRUCTURE OF FIELD ORIENTED CONTROL
- III. DROOP CONTROL IN PARALLEL VSIS
- IV. PROPOSED FOC-DROOP CONTROL STRATEGY
 - a. Theoretical basis of FOC-Droop control strategy
 - b. Implementation of FOC-Droop control strategy
- V. STABILITY AND SENSIBILITY ANALYSIS
- VI. SIMULATION RESULTS
- VII. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS
- VIII. CONCLUSION